

METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF CRITICAL PSYCHOLOGY

Abduvokhidova Nodirabegim Abduvosiq kizi

Psychologist at Kindermed Clinic

nbegim13@gmail.com

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Abstract. Modern ways are being developed in the world to prevent divorces, preserve the family as much as possible, work with families that have entered a state of divorce, and identify their causes and factors. The family is a sacred place for a person, the social foundation of human society. Due to the constant interdependence of family life and the development of society, family problems have been the focus of attention of its progressive representatives in all periods of society's development. In this article, we will cover divorces and their consequences.

Keywords: upbringing, spouses, children, dysfunctional family, divorce, interpersonal relationships, behavior.

Аннотация. В мире разрабатываются современные подходы к профилактике разводов, максимальному сохранению семьи, работе с семьями, находящимися в состоянии развода, выявлению причин и факторов, способствующих его возникновению. Семья – это святыня для человека, социальная основа человеческого общества. В силу постоянной взаимозависимости семейной жизни и развития общества, семейные проблемы находились в центре внимания его прогрессивных представителей на всех этапах развития. В данной статье мы рассмотрим разводы и их последствия.

Ключевые слова: воспитание, супруги, дети, неблагополучная семья, развод, межличностные отношения, поведение.

Introduction. In some countries of the world, including Italy and the Netherlands, divorce was a very complicated legal process until recently. However, this method also does not give the expected results in ensuring the strength of the family. Perhaps the prohibition of divorce, the denial of freedom to divorce, in turn, the increase in the age of marriage, the lack of family formation, premarital and extramarital sex, the increase in the number of psychologically unhealthy families, will lead to an increase in crimes, murder, betrayal, etc. that arise in the context of marital and family relations. Of course, these are no less harmful to the individual, the human psyche, the upbringing of children in the family, and society than before. That is why the freedom of divorce is currently enshrined in the marriage and family legislation of almost all countries. The important thing here is not to prohibit divorce and officially interfere with it, but to prevent divorces, eliminate the causes and factors that lead to it. So is divorce a tragedy or an escape from tragedy? Some believe that if there are no children in a family, this is an escape from tragedy. If the relationship between spouses is not developing as intended, if they lack mutual understanding, mutual respect, emotional closeness, and kindness towards each other, and if the family is not fulfilling its functions, then it is better for such couples to separate.

Discussion. Divorces have their own socio-psychological and ethno-psychological

characteristics. These characteristics are expressed in the reasons leading to the breakdown of families, the process of their implementation, consequences, the state of spouses before and after the divorce. One of these characteristics is reflected in who is the initiator of the divorce, who applies to official organizations with the intention of divorce. In Eastern families, especially in Uzbek (rural) families, more men are the initiators of divorce, and vice versa, in families of European peoples, young families and urban families with a high level of urbanization, more women are the initiators of divorce.[4]

The analysis shows that it is illogical to describe the conflicts and their causes inherent in all families in our country or abroad with a single dimension or characteristic. But by studying different types of families, comparing the relationships between their members, and so on, one can come to some relative conclusions and considerations, from which each person should draw relatively "appropriate" conclusions for himself. That is why we studied the experiences of several countries in our study.

Result and analysis. There are situations in the family when, precisely between husband and wife, a conflict arises, this conflict can be resolved through words, that is, through the culture of communication. Even in the most difficult period of financial hardship in the family, a sweet word, that is, a beautiful speech, from family members to each other can bring a person out of a state of depression, words have such power.

Uzbek psychologists M.G.Davletshin, V.M.Karimova, N.A.Soginov conducted research on interpersonal relationships in the family, relationships between spouses, conflicts, and socio-psychological, ethno-psychological characteristics of families of different nationalities in the region, the causes and consequences of divorces, extramarital affairs, remarriage, and child rearing in the family.[4]

Psychologist G.B.Shoumarov, who conducted a number of studies, studied conflicts between spouses, their causes, forms, external manifestations, and the issues of identifying and eliminating the initiator of the conflict in his scientific research on family relations.[4]

V.M.Karimova highlighted the impact of communication in interpersonal relationships in the family on the socialization of the individual, its specific role in the assimilation of social norms by the individual, and gave detailed scientific and practical recommendations. It is proven that it is necessary to study the perceptions of young people in family relationships in detail.[4]

F.R.Ro'zikulov's research revealed the socio-psychological complications of divorces in Uzbek families. He found that divorces in the family have a strong negative impact on the behavior, personality, and socio-economic conditions of the former husband and wife, their children, and that the negative complications of divorce in Uzbek families are stronger, more serious, and lead to negative individual-psychological and socio-economic consequences than in families of other nationalities.[5]

Ibragimova R.J. in her study noted the difficulty of determining the causes of family divorces, the fact that spouses who come to court never openly state the real reasons there, which has also been proven in world experience. IPS was developed to study the object of this research. In her study, she indicated 37 reasons in the questionnaire in order to identify the reasons that led to divorce. As a result, most of the information was obtained through this questionnaire, as well as interviews with divorced men and women.[3]

Tovbayeva M.S. studied the prevention of psychological despotism in gender relations in problematic families in her research. The research work studied which categories of problematic families are more likely to experience violence. As a result of the research, it was found that families with conflict, quarrelsome families, alcoholics, and families with previous convictions belong to the most dangerous group. She noted that family conflicts are one of the main reasons for encountering violence.[5]

According to the Russian sociologist S.Golod, all positive processes observed in the lives of European peoples and family relations occurred due to the preservation of the monogamous, patriarchal family, while all other negative situations, on the contrary, arise from negative, bad processes occurring in the family. Such arguments naturally prevent many researchers from understanding the family and its future, and from conducting serious research in this area.[1]

S.V.Kovalev noted that due to the lack of correct ideas about family life and lifestyle among young people, there are often cases of dissatisfaction with family and marital relations when they get married. Therefore, he puts forward valuable advice on creating educational conditions in the places where young people grow up and study, preparing them for family life and marriage, forming in them the necessary qualities and qualities that ensure a happy family and a prosperous life, and saving them from romantic, sweet fantasies about the future family, and various distractions.[2]

Conclusion. Based on the above considerations, although many scientific research studies have been conducted on the study of divorce and its causes, it is appropriate to approach all the ideas put forward in them taking into account the regional situations and weddings consisting of various invented "customs", the modern lifestyle that is changing from year to year, and the dreams of young people. During our research, we decided to study divorces as a socio-psychological phenomenon and to conduct research by dividing the causes and factors that cause them into main groups.

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